

Evaluation of Anti-inflammatory and Anti-diabetic Activities of *Bryophyllum pinnatum*

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The present study aimed to evaluate the in vitro anti-inflammatory and anti-diabetic potential of aqueous leaf extract of *B. pinnatum*. **Methods:** The leaves of *B. pinnatum* were collected and extracted with water. Qualitative phytochemical tests were performed using standard methods. The anti-inflammatory activity of *B. pinnatum* leaf extract was evaluated by protein denaturation analysis, membrane stabilization activity and proteinase inhibition activity. Anti-diabetic activity was assessed by alpha-amylase inhibitory activity. **Results:** Based on the in vitro studies, dose dependent and significant ($p < 0.05$) anti-inflammatory activity and anti-diabetic activity was observed. **Conclusion:** Results from the present study revealed that the leaves of *B. pinnatum* possessed significant anti-inflammatory and anti-diabetic potential. However, further pharmacological investigation and in vivo studies in animal models need to be performed to confirm its efficacy and mechanism of action.

Keywords: Anti-Inflammatory Activity, *B. Pinnatum*, Anti-Diabetic Activity, Membrane Stabilization, Proteinase Inhibition

INTRODUCTION

Phytochemicals of medicinal plants are the source of medicines for curing various health ailments (Bachheti et al., 2020). As the inventory list WHO reported, greater than 20,000 species of medicinal plants have been compiled so far (Vaou et al., 2021). Inflammation is a biological defense mechanism that permits living cells to protect themselves against diseases (Dharmaveda et al., 2018). The inflammatory response is effective by exudation of different mediators responsible for the initiation, progression, persistence, regulation and resolution of inflammation effects (Oguntibeju, 2018).

Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are used for the management and treatment of inflammation. The practice of NSAIDs for anti-inflammatory diseases has not been therapeutically successful in severe conditions of inflammation (Hajhashemi et al., 2009). Moreover, adverse effects associated with NSAIDs can lead to conditions such as ulcer and hemorrhage.

Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disorder characterized by chronic hyperglycemia resulting from defects in insulin secretion. Diabetes mellitus is affecting millions of people all over the world and the number of people affecting by it is increasing day by day. Diabetes will be the seventh top source of death in 2030, according to the World Health Organization (Saleemm and Ain, 2023). Moreover, the insistently raised sugar level induces damage of various organs. The currently available modern drugs used for the treatment of diabetes are related with limitations such as insufficient efficacy and various side effects. In view of the aforementioned drawbacks of conventional medicines, medicinal plants with antidiabetic activity can be used as alternative approach in the management of diabetes. The increasing bacterial resistance to antibiotics during the treatment of inflammatory diseases and Diabetes mellitus has become a growing concern worldwide (Gardam, 2000). Intensive care physicians consider antibiotic-resistant bacteria a foremost problem (Lepape and Monne, 2009). Increasing bacterial resistance is a prompting resurgence in research of the

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antimicrobial role of medicinal plants against resistant strains (Alviano and Alviano, 2009). Therefore, to surpass the anti-microbial resistance and to find a more safe and efficient therapeutic option, researchers are considering plants as a source of medicine. According to the World Health Organization nearly 80% of the world population prefers plant-based drugs (Dharmasiri et al., 2003). The research on screening and development of plant-based drugs is therefore, an unending process. The compounds isolated from medicinal plants have proved as a good and safe anti-inflammatory agent (Cardile et al., 2009). Latest **studies** have reported the beneficial aspects of plant derived drugs as good source of antibiotics, antioxidants and anti-inflammatory agents (Mutassim et al., 2013).

Bryophyllum pinnatum (family: Crassulaceae) is also referred as *Kalanchoe pinnatum*. It is 3 to 6 meters high perennial herb and has opposed glabrous leaves (Kamboj and Saluja, 2017). The herb contains a wide range of phytochemicals that could be accountable for its various pharmacological effects (Jaiswal and Sawhney, 2006). Around the globe, it is consumed for the treatment and management of various diseases and conditions such as cuts, conjunctivitis, edema, piles, epilepsy, cholera, asthma, menstrual disorders, chicken pox, insect bites, psychiatric disorders and abdominal discomforts (Sadhana et al., 2017). However, to the best of our knowledge, very little research on anti-inflammatory and anti-diabetic effect have been studied in the leaves of *B. pinnatum*. Hence, effort is being made here to investigate the anti-inflammatory and anti-diabetic activities of aqueous leaf extract of *B. pinnatum*.

METHODOLOGY

Sample collection : The leaves of *B. pinnatum* were collected from 45 days old plant in a nursery garden near Alagar kovil hills. The plant was authenticated by the Department of Botany, Lady Doak College, Madurai. The leaves were washed in sterile water and air-dried at room temperature. Dried leaves were powdered (20g) and extracted with 100mL of distilled water using Soxhlet extractor for 48h. The extract was filtered using Whatmann No.1 filter paper and stored at 4° C. The aqueous extract was subjected to qualitative phytochemical analysis.

Screening of Phytochemical constituents: Phytochemical screening of the *B. pinnatum* leaf extract was executed to detect the presence of various phytoconstituents by standard methods (Manjamalai et al., 2010). The results of qualitative phytochemical tests are stated as (+) for the presence and (-) for the absence of phytoconstituents.

GC-MS Analysis: GC-MS chromatogram of the *B. pinnatum* leaf extract was obtained by Perki Elmer /Turbo Mass spectrophotometer (Norwalk, CTO6858 and USA) using Helium as a carrier gas with a flow rate of 0.5mL/min. The extract was injected and temperature of the inlet was set at 250° C. The temperature programme of the oven was set initially at 110° C for 4 min, and then increased up to 280° C. The spectrum of the plant components was related with the database of the spectrum of known compounds stored in the GC-MS NIST (2008) library.

EVALUTION OF ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY

Inhibition of protein denaturation: The anti-inflammatory activity of aqueous extract of *B. pinnatum* was evaluated by following the procedure of Leelaprakash and Mohan (2011). The reaction mixture consisted of 0.5ml bovine serum albumin and 0.5 mL of 100-500 µg/mL of *B. pinnatum* leaf extract. Samples were incubated at 37° C for and then heated at 57° C for 3 min. After cooling the samples, 2.5ml of phosphate buffer saline (pH 6.3) was added and absorbance was measured spectrophotometrically at 660nm. Percentage inhibition of protein denaturation was calculated. IC50 value of extract and standard was also calculated.

$$\text{Percentage inhibition (\%)} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of control} - \text{Absorbance of test}}{\text{Absorbance of control}} \times 100$$

Effect on Membrane Stabilization : The membrane stabilizing activity of *B.pinnatum* was evaluated by following the procedure of Chioma et al. (2012). The reaction mixture consisted of hypotonic saline, varying concentrations of aqueous *B. pinnatum* leaf extract (100-500ug/mL) and 10% RBC in normal saline. The mixture was incubated at 50° C for 30 minutes. The mixture was centrifuged for 3000rpm for 10 min. and the absorbance of the supernatant was

measured at 560nm. The percentage membrane stabilization was calculated. IC50 value of extract and standard (diclofenac) was also calculated.

$$\text{Membrane stabilization (\%)} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of control} - \text{Absorbance of test}}{\text{Absorbance of control}} \times 100$$

Proteinase inhibitory assay: The proteinase inhibitory activity of the aqueous extract of *B.pinnatum* was assessed as per Brindha et al. (2014). The reaction mixtures consisted of trypsin, tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.4), casein (0.8%) and varying concentrations of aqueous *B. pinnatum* leaf extract. The mixture was incubated at 37° C for 10 min. Perchloric acid 70% (v/v) was added to terminate the reaction. The suspension was centrifuged and the absorbance was measured at 280nm. Proteinase inhibitory activity of the *B. pinnatum* leaf extract and standard was calculated.

EVALUTION OF ANTI-DIABETIC ACTIVITY

Alpha - amylase inhibition assay: The Alpha-amylase inhibition of *B. pinnatum* leaf extract was measured by following the procedure of Chirumamilla and Taduri (2023). The samples were mixed with alpha-amylase solution (0.5 mg/mL) and incubated for 10 min at RT. Subsequently, 0.5 mL sodium phosphate buffer (0.02M) with 1% starch was added and incubated. The reaction was stopped immediately by adding DNSA reagent and boiled for 5 min at 95° C. The tubes were cooled and the final

volume was set to 10 mL by addition of distilled water (Kusuma et al., 2018). The absorbance of the samples was measured at 540 nm and the percentage inhibition of alpha-amylase was calculated. Acarbose was used as standard drug.

Results and Discussion: The therapeutic characteristics of medicinal plants are mainly because of the presence of diversified secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, polyphenols, steroids, flavanoids, terpenoids, and coumarins (Eftekhari et al., 2021). Among the various medicinal plants *B.pinnatum* is a herb of the Crassulaceae family, with varied pharmacological activity. In the present study the phytochemical constituents of *B.pinnatum* were found to be alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, phenols and carbohydrates (Table1). These phytochemicals compounds may demonstrate anti-inflammatory effects by blocking the lipoxygenase pathway. Terpenoids are recognized for their ability to suppress histamine release and exhibit anti-inflammatory properties (Shilpa et al., 2018). Alkaloids are acknowledged for their ability to reduce joint swelling, lower arthritic severity and regulate levels of IL-1 β and TNF- α in the inflamed tissues of arthritic rats (Sindhu and Manorama, 2013). Hence, it could be suggested that the anti-inflammatory effects of the plant's aqueous extract may be attributed to a synergistic combination of flavonoids, tannins, terpenoids and alkaloids present in the aqueous leaf extract of *B.pinnatum*.

Table 1. Phytochemical screening of *B. pinnatum* leaf extract

Phytochemicals	Test	Observation	Inference
Carbohydrates	Molisch's test	purple ring at the interface.	+
Protein & Amino acid	Ninhydrin reagent	Purple color formation	+
Alkaloids	Mayer's test	Cream colored precipitate	+
Flavonoids	Alkaline reagent test	Deep yellow color	+
Phenol	Test with ferric chloride	Dark blue	+
Tannins	Test with ferric chloride	Dark blue	+
Saponins	Foam test	No foam formation	-
Steroids	Salkowski test	Red color	+
Terpenoids	Salkowski test	Reddish brown coloration of the inter face	+
Glycosides	Keller-Kiliani Test	No violet ring formation	-

Gas chromatography (GC) and mass spectrometry (MS) is an essential technique for analysing the presence of various chemical compounds of medicinal importance. Gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS) synergizes two potent methodologies to offer compound identification with high sensitivity and the capacity for quantitative assessment. The mass spectrometer analyses the nature and structure of the compounds. The large compound fragments into small compounds giving rise to appearance of peaks at different m/z ratios.

In the present study, the aqueous leaf extract B.pinnatum was subjected to GC-MS analysis. The

compounds with their peak area (%), retention time (RT), molecular formula, molecular weight and structure are presented in figure 1. The aqueous leaf extract of B. Pinnatum revealed 10 major compounds and based on the maximum peak area (%) and retention time such as 1,4,8-Cycloundecatriene, Di-n-octylphthalate, seychellene, 1H-Cyclopenta [1,3] Cyclopropa [1,2], Gleenol, 8-Isopropyl-1,3-Dimethyltricyclo, n-Hexadecanoic acid, 1,6,9-Tetradecatriene, Cubenol 3-Phenylbutanol were reported prime components in the aqueous extract. The presence of various bioactive compounds confirms the therapeutic applications of B.pinnatum (Janakiraman et al., 2012).

Figure 1 GC-MS chromatogram of B. pinnatum leaf extract

Protein denaturation is widely acknowledged to play a role in inflammatory conditions such as rheumatoid arthritis, diabetes and cancer. During protein denaturation, proteins lose its confirmation due to the presence of other compounds, external stress, heat and

leads to loss of the biological function of proteins. Various research on inflammation reports that denaturation of tissue proteins is recognized as an important marker of inflammation. Protein denaturation entails the disruption of its secondary,

tertiary and quaternary structures, ultimately resulting in cellular demise. The denaturation mechanism involves modifications in electrostatic, hydrogen, hydrophobic, and disulfide bonding.

In the present study, the in vitro anti-inflammatory activity of *B. pinnatum* leaf extract was assessed for

inhibitory activity against protein denaturation. The *B. pinnatum* leaf extract had an inhibition of 74.74%. However, the standard anti-inflammatory drug exhibited 86.12% inhibition at a concentration of 500 µg/mL (Table 2).

Table 2 – Effect of *B. pinnatum* leaf extract on protein denaturation

Concentration (µg/mL)	Percentage inhibition	
	<i>B. pinnatum</i> leaf extract	Standard
100	24.77±0.61	34.12±1.66
200	39.28±1.75	46.25±1.50
300	51.73±2.48	62.16±1.42
400	64.28±0.67	72.85±2.48
500	74.74±1.37	86.12±0.63
IC₅₀ value of <i>B. pinnatum</i> leaf extract - 292 (µg/mL)		
IC₅₀ value of Standard drug – 220 (µg/mL)		

All the values are expressed as mean ±SEM (n=3)

All the values are significant when compared to control p<0.05

Stabilizing effect on heat and saline induced erythrocyte lysis is very good index of anti-inflammatory activity. The membrane of RBC is similar to that of lysosomal membrane. In inflammatory condition stabilising the lysosomal membrane helps to prevent the release of lysosomal

constituents of activated neutrophil such as proteases and bactericidal enzymes which cause further tissue inflammation and damage upon extra cellular release. In inflammatory scenarios, stabilizing the lysosomal membrane helps mitigate the release of lysosomal constituents from activated neutrophils, including proteases and bactericidal enzymes. In the present study, the *B. pinnatum* leaf extract showed the highest membrane stabilization activity of 70.85% whereas the standard drug had a membrane stabilization activity of 86.24% (Table 3).

Table 3 – Membrane stabilization effect *B. pinnatum* leaf extract

Concentration (µg/mL)	Membrane stabilization (%)	
	<i>B. pinnatum</i> leaf extract	Standard
100	20.56±0.48	27.13±0.54
200	32.84±2.35	36.49±1.63
300	47.21±1.64	55.17±0.74
400	58.74±1.75	68.48±2.85
500	70.85±1.95	86.24±1.64
IC₅₀ value of <i>B. pinnatum</i> leaf extract - 372 (µg/mL)		
IC₅₀ value of Standard drug – 286 (µg/mL)		

All the values are expressed as mean ±SEM (n=3)

All the values are significant when compared to control p<0.05

Proteinase are involved in inflammatory reactions since leucocyte proteinases are reported to play a vital role in tissue damage development during inflammatory reactions. Previous studies have

highlighted the crucial role of leucocyte proteinases in tissue damage during inflammatory reactions, with proteinase inhibitors offering significant protection. In the present study the proteinase inhibitory activity of *B.pinnatum* leaf extract was found to be 64.75%.

Figure 2. Effect of aqueous *B. pinnatum* leaf extract on Proteinase inhibitory activity

Alpha amylase enzyme have been recognized as therapeutic targets to modulation of postprandial hyperglycemia since they are known to reduce postprandial hyperglycemia by partially inhibiting the enzymatic hydrolysis of complex carbohydrates and hence may delay the absorption of glucose. Acarbose, voglibose and miglitol are synthetic inhibitors used either alone or in combination for patients with type II diabetics. However, these inhibitors are reported to cause several side effects. Hence, several other safer natural inhibitors are reported from plant resources. The discovery of novel and safe anti-diabetic agents from plant sources is of enormous demand at present due to increased prevalence of diabetes at global level. Plethora of plants has been investigated in the past to identify potential anti-diabetic agents (Salehi et al., 2019). However, identifying ideal anti-diabetic agents from natural resources is an ongoing process. Considering this, an attempt was undertaken in the present study to determine the in vitro anti-diabetic characteristics of *B. Pinnatum* leaf extract. The alpha-amylase inhibitory activity of *B. pinnatum* was found to be in a dose-dependent manner. The *B. pinnatum* leaf extract had an alpha amylase inhibitory activity of 71% whereas the standard drug had an inhibitory activity of 88.15% (Figure 3).

Figure 3. alpha –amylase inhibition activity of *B.pinnatum* leaf extract

CONCLUSION

The present study reports the in vitro therapeutic potential of *B.pinnatum* leaf extract. The crude extract exhibited a significant in vitro antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and alpha- amylase inhibitory activity. Further, it is indispensable to conduct future studies in isolation and characterization of bioactive compound(s) responsible for its various therapeutic activity and postulate the possible mechanism of action and efficacy in regular intake. Further in vivo studies in animal model is essential to elucidate the possible mechanism of action of *B.pinnatum* leaf extract at biochemical and molecular level.

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